

Relationship of Parental Acceptance and Problem-Solving Ability Among Young Adolescents in Anambra State.

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Abstract

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain the relationship between Parental acceptance and problem solving ability among young adolescents in Anambra State. Three research questions guided the study. The sample was 2,950 JS 3 students in Anambra State. A 35-item researcher made questionnaire was used to collect data. The questionnaire was duly validated by experts with a reliability co-efficient of 0.82 which was considered okay for the study. Analysis of data was done using mean and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient. Findings from the study reveal that there is a positive relationship of parental acceptance and problem solving ability of their children. Recommendations include that parents should review the interaction process existing in their family.

Introduction

One's ability to get on in life depends on one's ability to solve problems that one comes across. This is because problems must come and problem solving is a stepping stone to better life in this planet earth. Problem - solving has long historical roots in educational psychology and this is why it is one of the different components of individual creativity. Problem-solving has been defined as a higher order cognitive process that requires the modulation and control of more routine or fundamental skills (Goldstein & Levin, 1987). Henson and Eller (1999) outlined three approaches to problem- solving namely random search, brainstorming and using specific finite set of steps. Laudon & Laudon, (1999), observed that Dewey's pragmatic approach adopted four steps to problem-solving; identification, development of hypothesis, testing hypothesis and selection of best hypothesis. In line with the above Khandwalla (1997) noted that problem-solving has the following techniques; brainstorming, attribute-listing, checklist of questions and filling together diverse elements. He went on to say that problems are classified, according to difficulty categories whether it is open ended or not and by finding out what prevents one from solving the problem.

Squire & Stein (2003) observed that even though many children spend a great deal of time in child-care situations, parents are still the main care-givers for the vast majority of children. Lindgreen (1980) and Veneziano (2003) believed that the parents - child encounter results into a form of learning which will dictate the direction of the child's academic performance. According to Albert (1980), the interaction existing between the parents and children, when it is positive, leads to the acquisition of problems - solving abilities. No wonder, Mgboro (2005) and Rohner (2004a) described this positive interaction as parental acceptance of the children and went on to say that parental acceptance concerns the search, verification and prediction of the psychological environment on different dimensions of the child's development. Children who receive attention from the parents, whose parents are less authoritative, children with positive self esteem arising from the encouragement and support of ' their parents, children who play, discuss and share experiences with parents, are better able to solve their problems(Rohner,2004b). Similarly Elshout (1993) and Kin & Rohner (2000) noted that the freedom given to children to explore their environment, hugging, kissing; fondling, cuddling, praising, and comforting the child are signs of parental acceptance. Parents play the role of facilitators in a child's development of problem - solving ability (Master, 2001). But it is not really what the parents do but how the children perceive and interpret the parents' action that determine the child's development of problem-solving abilities.

The Problem

In Nigeria, including Anambra State the parents believe that adolescents are still young to form a part of decision making process in the home. Thus these adolescents tend to lag behind in problem solving later in life. This lagging behind in problem solving ability of these adolescents maybe as a result of lack of parental acceptance. It is against this background that the researcher was motivated to find out the relationship between parental acceptance and he adolescents' problem solving ability. Therefore the purpose of the study is to find out the relationship of parental acceptance as perceived by the adolescents' and their problem solving ability.

The study is guided by these three research questions:

Research Questions

1. What are the attributes of parental acceptance as perceived by the adolescents?
2. What are the components of problem-solving as perceived by adolescents?
3. To what extent does parental acceptance relate to the adolescents' problem solving ability?

Research Method

Research Design

The research design employed in carrying out this study was a correlational research design. This type of design is useful in studies that seek to establish what relationship exists between two or more variables (Akuezuilo & Agu 2003). Thus, this design is considered adequate for the present study, which seeks to find out the relationship of parental acceptance and problem-solving ability among adolescents in Anambra State.

Population and Area of study

The study was carried out in all the six education zones centrally managed by the Anambra State Universal Basic Education Board (Asubeb) in terms of students' enrolment and school curriculum in Anambra State. The population was all the 29,593 Junior secondary school students in all the 229 Junior secondary schools in Anambra state.

The total population was 29,593 as at 2007. (Source-planning, research and statistics department, State Education Commission, Awka)

Sample and Sampling Technique

The researcher used proportionate stratified sampling technique to select 2,960 junior secondary three students which represented 10% of the entire population which according to Akuezuilo and Agu (2003) is appropriate for a correctional study.

Instrument for Data Collection.

The instrument is a researcher-made questionnaire of 35 items. The instrument consists of sections A and B, Section A consisted of bio data of the respondents while section B had 35 items which was used to determine the relationship of parental acceptance and problem-solving ability among adolescents in Anambra State. The questionnaire was titled 'Parental acceptance and Adolescents' problem-solving ability Questionnaire' (PAAPSAQ). The respondents were requested to indicate for each item the extent to which they agreed that parental acceptance was related to their problem-solving ability. The extent of agreeableness was measured on a 4-point scales of strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed for research questions one and two. Research question three was measured from very high extent to very low extent.

Validation of the instrument

The face and content validity of the instrument were established by two experts; one from the Department of Guidance and Counselling and one from Psychology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The recommendations and suggestions of these experts were useful in the final modification and in the draft of the items in the questionnaire.

Reliability of the instrument

To establish reliability, 40 copies of the questionnaire were administered to 40 pilot test students in the Junior Secondary Schools in Delta State which were not used in the main study. The rationale for using the Delta State, was to avoid contamination with students in Anambra State where the main study was conducted. Using the odd and even numbered items technique, scores on the items were pooled and correlated using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. This yielded a co- efficient value of intenal consistency $r= 0.82$. The application of the Spearman-Brown Prophecy formula yielded a correlation value $r= 0.90$.

Collection of Data

The instrument was administered by the researcher to the subjects with the help of teachers in the schools. The researchers collected all the filled questionnaire sheets so there was no loss.

Data Analysis

The research questions one and two were answered using mean scores. For decision making items- scoring 2.50 and above were accepted. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was employed to find out the relationship of parental acceptance and adolescent problem solving ability for research question three.

Results

The data collected were tallied and analyzed. The results were then presented in sequential manner.

Table

Elements of parental Acceptance as perceived by students.

SIN	Item	Mean
1	Kiss	2.80
2	Hug	3.00
3	Fondle	2.90
4.	Praise	3.10
5	Compliment	3.00
6.	Comforting words	3.40
7.	Encouragement	3.20
8.	Playing with parents	3.50
9	Sharing experiences	3.10
10.	Cuddle	3.30
11.	Give freedom to explore the environment	3.40
12.	Positive reinforcement	3.20
13.	Confidence	3.50
14.	Attention	3.30
15.	Free discussion	3.40
16.	Support by parents in times of need	3.50

Table 1 reveals that the students agreed that all the elements above are all items of parental acceptance. This implies that all the items are elements of parental acceptance.

Table 2

Problem - solving techniques as perceived by adolescents.

Items	Mean
1. Trial and error	2.90
2. Random search	2.80
3. Guesswork	2.70
4. Going from known to unknown	3.70
5. Brainstorming	3.40
6. Using specific set of steps	3.50
7. Identification of the problem	3.00
8. Development of hypothesis	3.20
9. Testing hypothesis	3.40
10. Selection of best alternative	2.50
11. Understanding the problem	3.60
12. Means - ends analysis	3.30
13. Transfer of previous knowledge	3.50
14. Thinking of unusual ideas	2.70
15. Planning	2.80
16. Generating many ideas	3.50
17. Mapping the possibilities	3.00
18. Assembling the facts	2.90
19. Getting the problem clearly	3.60

Table 2 also reveals that the students agreed that all the techniques above are all items of problem solving. This implies that all the items are elements of problem solving.

Table 3:

Variable	Number of Students	Sum of scores	Sum of Students square	XY	r	Remarks
Parental Acceptance	2960	12378	7876005			
Problem Solving	2960	14436	9642342	7434035	0.82	+ve

From table 3 above the Product Moment Correlation Coefficient $r = 0.82$. Following this therefore there was a positive relationship of parental acceptance and problem solving ability among young adolescents. Summary of findings

- The elements investigated were all items of parental acceptance as perceived by the students.

- The items investigated were all techniques of problem solving perceived by the students.
- There was a positive relationship between parental acceptance and students problem-solving ability.

Discussion

The findings in table one indicated that the students accepted all the items - kissing, hugging, fondling, praising, complementing, comforting words, encouragement, playing with parents, sharing experiences, cuddle, giving freedom to exploring the environment, positive reinforcement, confidence, attention and free discussion as parental acceptance elements. The finding was expected because each item of the relationship has a potentiality of bringing comfort and pleasure in the home. No wonder Elshout (1993) earlier listed exploring the environment, hugging, kissing, fondling, cuddling, praising and comforting as signs of parental acceptance. These signs will continued to be signs of parental acceptance in the future since parents are still the main care givers as noted by Santrock (2000).The finding in table two shows that trial and error, random search, guess work, going from known to unknown, brainstorming, using specific set of steps, identification,, developing and testing hypothesis, transfer of previous knowledge, mapping getting the problem clearly and planning amongst others are all techniques, of problem-solving. This is in line with Henson and Eller (1999) and Amato and Fowler(2002); who outlined random search, means-ends analysis, brainstorming, using specific set of steps as; techniques of problem solving.

The findings in table 3 revealed that there was a significant relationship between parental acceptance and students' problem solving ability. The result of the findings indicated that where parental acceptance was high, then the students' ability to solve problem increased This is inline with Rutter (1979), Lindgreen (1980) and Rohner (2004b) assertion that parents who interact with their children by discussing, staying and playing with them provide opportunities for the children to explore their environment and solve their problems.

Conclusion

The study focused on the relationship of parental acceptance and problem solving ability among students in Anambra State. The ability of the student to solve problem as revealed in the study has been conceptualized in terms of the amount of freedom the child has to participate in decision-making, exploring the environment and verbal stimulation by the parents among others.

Recommendations

In the light of the above, the following recommendations are made-

1. Parents should review the interaction processes existing in their families.
2. Counsellor in the school should organize a seminar or workshop involving the parents of the students. This will help them to adopt a better parenting style for a better problem solving ability of their children.
3. The relationship of parents with their children should be strengthened by staying, discussing and playing together.

4. Counsellors should encourage students to be involved in their school decision making as it affects them.

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